

“SEMANTIC CHARACTERISTICS OF WHOLE - PART RELATIONSHIPS RELATED TO HOUSEHOLD APPLIANCES IN UZBEK AND ENGLISH”

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Abstract: This paper studies general semantic and lexicographic properties of meronymic elements which are related to household appliances in Uzbek and English. The study examines how household appliance terms are named in the two languages, their division into different parts, how whole-part relations are reflected in dictionaries, and how they express the cultural and logical features of both languages. It also shows how linguistic changes occur when using the meronymic system to represent the structure of an object. The thesis determines the similarities and differences between English and Uzbek and is prepared using the method of contrastive, lexicographic and corpus analysis.

Key words: semantic characteristics, English, Uzbek, lexicography, semantic analysis, meronym, home appliances, and language comparison

Annotatsiya: Ushbu tadqiqot o'zbek va ingliz tillarida uy ro'zg' (maishiy texnika) bilan bog'liq meronimik birliklarning semantik va leksikografik xususiyatlarini o'rganadi. Tadqiqotda maishiy texnika atamalarining ikki tilda qanday nomlanishi, ularning turli qismlarga bo'linishi, meronimlarning lug'atlarda qanday aks etishi, har ikki tilning madaniy va mantiqiy xususiyatlarini qanday ifodalashi o'rganiladi. Bundan tashqari, ob'ekt tuzilishini ifodalash uchun meronomik tizimdan foydalanganda qanday lingvistik o'zgarishlar sodir bo'lishini ko'rsatadi. Maqolada ingliz tili va o'zbek tili o'rtasidagi o'xshashlik va farqlar yoritilgan va kontrastli, leksikografik va corpusli tahlillar usulidan foydalangan holda tayyorlangan.

Kalit so'zlar: semantik xususiyatlari, ingliz, o'zbek, leksikografiya, semantik tahlil, meronim, uy-ro'zg'or buyumlari (maishiy texnika) va til taqqoslash.

Introduction: In linguistics, whole -part relations (meronyms) are of vital importance in the study of the semantic connection between an object and its components. Meronyms are relationships that form an object hierarchy from the whole to the parts. As a practical manifestation of the meronymic system, expressions related to household appliances, i.e. household items, which are often used in everyday life, are especially important. This article compares the lexical composition, methods of reflection and semantic properties of meronymic units expressing the function of household appliances, in particular, the whole object related to our daily life, in Uzbek and English dictionaries. Terms for common household objects such as a table, a sofa and a door, as well as the names and constructions of their components, are the main topics of analysis. The aim of the article was to show the logical and cultural foundations of meronyms and to show the similarities and contrasts between them in the English and Uzbek lexical systems.

Methods: The use meronyms as language elements in linguistics, especially in our daily life part and to study them analytically as a separate topic has been highlighted by English researchers in their scientific works in the form of practical examples. In world linguistics, the scientist M.V. Nikitin [11:1988] who covered the concept of meronym in a broader sense, introduced the study of the whole and its partial elements as semantic-structural meaning individuality into the science.[22:1996] In Uzbek linguistics, B. Kilichev,[3:2019] A. Sobirov [2:2019] were the first to speak about the concepts of meronym (part-whole) relations, and H. Nematov and R. Rasulov, B. Kilichev [17:1986] and H. Jamolkhonov [4:2005] provided information in their research works about “paronyms” expand the vocabulary.[6:2005] D. A. Kolodka [8:1971]; N. Kuzmenka [21:2020]; V.Zakharov [9:2005] and E. O.Materinski [7:2019] are also known as researchers who have widely promoted the scope of research on both linguistic and cognitive principles of the meronymic concept. Today, many Uzbek researchers and researchers are conducting extensive research on meronymic words. In this regard, B. Kilichev “Whole-Part Relationships Between Words in Lexicon”, Eshmuminov A.A.[1:2023] “Formation of a linguistic base of taxonomic and meronymic related lexemes for Uzbek language corpora” who contributed to the research on meronymy and its various aspects, such as its classification, lexical representation, and cross-linguistics features in English and Uzbek. their works have laid a foundation for understanding how part-whole relationships are encoded in different languages and how these relationships can be systematically described in lexicographic and corpus-based studies. S.U.Mustafaeva [6:2025] has explained clear explanation about the use of meronymy in Uzbek and English in her “Uzbek and English dialects are used as examples to illustrate the problems with vocabulary creation in meronymy”. In presenting this work on the basis of theoretical ideas and in examples of their practical analysis. The theoretical analyses in our study are underpinned by the following key methodologies:

- a) **Descriptive method** — This method allows for the analysis of meronymic units in both Uzbek and English, determining their role in the lexicographic process. For example, this method was used to study the types of meronymy used in Uzbek and English and how these units are included in dictionaries;
- b) **Comparative method** — This technique allows us to compare the representation of meronymic units in Uzbek and English dictionaries. It examines how meronymic meanings are classified in English dictionaries and how such units are explained in Uzbek dictionaries. Furthermore, the similarities and differences in the use of meronymy between the two languages were analyzed using this approach;
- c) **Structural-Semantic Method** — This method focuses on the study of the structure of word meanings in dictionaries. It is particularly useful in analyzing how meronymic changes occur. Questions such as: “How are the primary and meronymic meanings of a word interconnected?” and “Which meanings are designated as primary in the dictionary, and which are secondary?” can be answered through this method;
- d) **Lexicographic Analysis** — This method is essential in the theory of dictionary-making. It allows for an investigation into how meronymic units are incorporated and explained in various dictionaries, thus defining the scope of their expression. The differences in the stylistic approaches to presenting meronymic meanings in Uzbek and English dictionaries

were also explored through this methodology. Through lexicographic analysis, we observed the dialectal variations in the usage and expression of meronymic words in the two languages;

Discussions and results

By analyzing we first consider meronyms in the context of the Princeton WordNet (PWN), a lexical database widely used in the world of English lexicography, which is a key resource for understanding English lexicon when it comes to meronymy. It organizes words into sets of synonyms (synsets) and includes detailed semantic relationships such as meronymy. To determine the meronymic words in English, we can address the English dictionaries such as “Cambridge Advanced Learner’s Dictionary”, “Longman Dictionary of Contemporary English”, “Oxford Dictionary” and etc. The interpretation of meronymic words in Uzbek dictionaries is not specific, but they are defined as part of a certain object or phenomenon from a given context, we analyzed them by selecting words related to meronymic relations from the “Explanatory Dictionary of the Uzbek Language”. In her article “Uzbek and English dialects are given as examples to illustrate the problems associated with creating a dictionary in meronymy”, S.U. Mustafayeva gives an idea of how meronymic relations, that is, part-whole relations, are expressed and sheds light on the phenomenon of how “part”/ “share”/ “piece” are expressed in the compared Uzbek and English languages. By comparing the above-mentioned sources, it is possible to observe how linguistic, cognitive and lexicographic factors affect the expression of meronymy. In this, the analysis reveals similarities and differences in the processing of parts and wholes in the two languages, enriching our understanding of their lexical systems and cognitive structures.

1. Picture

When searching the meronymy from the WordNet-Online (Free dictionary and thesaurus of English. Definitions, synonyms, antonyms and more...) it shows like that:

Definitions from WordNet

Noun **meronym** has 1 sense

1. **meronym**, part name - a word that names a part of a larger whole; "brim' and 'crown' are meronyms of 'hat'"
 --> is a kind of word

Definitions from the Web

Term: **Meronym**

Definition:

A meronym is a term used in linguistics and semantic theory to describe a part or member of something larger. In this context, it refers to words that represent components, elements, or parts of a whole.

Example sentences:

1. The word "leaf" is a meronym of the word "tree."

From the "Cambridge English dictionary" meronym is determined as a component of something, such as "bud" has got 172 meanings as part of something, it is following that:

In Uzbek dictionaries, especially, regional dialects such as Tashkent, Fergana, Samarkhand and Surkhandarya Uzbek exhibit variations in meronymic terms for household items. For example, in "Explanatory dictionary of the Uzbek language" " chovgun"

2. Picture

ЧОВГУН Ўтда чой қайнатиш учун мос-
 ланган идиш, чойдиш, қумфон. *Мис човгун.*
Чўян човгун. Човгунда чой қайнатмоқ. ■
[Севаргул] Рўмолчани сувга тутиб, обдан
ишқалади, сўнг кўҳна мис човгунни тўлатиб,
жўмракни маҳкамлади. Н. Қўличев, Чигирик,

which is related to dialectal words in Surkhandarya region, meaning dishes that is used as a kettle but it can be used in the fire pit to boil the water. Similarly, in English, dialects such as American, British, and Australian English show distinctions in part-whole relationships, with words like "tap" (British) versus "faucet" (American) exemplifying lexical differences. These variations illustrate how languages adapt to local contexts while maintaining core semantic relationships. This study categorizes meronyms from both languages into distinct lexical groups, including furniture, kitchenware, clothing, and tools, highlighting their

structural and semantic patterns. By analyzing dialectal influences, we aim to provide a comprehensive understanding of how meronymy shapes vocabulary development and communication. The findings contribute to broader discussions in lexicology, cognitive linguistics, and comparative language studies, offering valuable insights for linguists, educators, and language learners alike. This introduction establishes the foundation for your study, connecting meronymy to vocabulary formation and dialectal variations in Uzbek and English.

A dictionary of meronyms in the Uzbek and English languages, describing them as “part” - “whole” form-levels in the type of household appliances.

A dictionary of words forming partial forms of the whole meaning of “House” in the Uzbek and English languages.

- Household items:

№	meronimlar	O'zbek tilida sharhlanishi	Ingliz tilida sharhlanishi
1.	adyol	adiyol - ko'rpa o'rnida ishlatiladigan yengil, uncha qalin bo'lmagan yoping'ich	blanket - a light, not very thick cover
2.	ayoq	kosa, payola, qadah	“ayak” - cup, goblet
3.	angishvona	ko'rpa qavishda barmoq uchiga kiyiladigan metal vosita	“angishvona” - a metal tool worn on the tip of a finger when sewing a quilt
4.	arga / dok sozi	arga - bu yog'ochdan yasalgan katta dastgoh o'lib gilam yoki boshqa matolarni to'qish uchun ishlatiladi	“agra” - is a large wooden machine used to weave carpets or other fabrics.
5.	aroba (arava)	arava - bu ikki yoki to'rt g'ildirakli ot, eshak yoki ho'kiz qo'shiladigan transport vositasi	a cart is a two- or four-wheeled vehicle pulled by a horse, donkey, or ox.
6.	araqi	karniz alyumini metalidan tayyorlanadigan uzun shakldagi truba qaysiki parda ilish uchun foydalaniladi	“arakhi” - a long, aluminum tube used to hang curtains
7.	Badya	yog'och, sandiq, yoki metaldan yasalgan maxsus katta idish	“badya” - a large container made of wood, a crate, or metal
8.	Bak	tog'ora; suv isitish, choy qaynatishga mo'ljallangan, samovarga o'xshash katta metal idish	“bak” - a washingbasin; a large metal teapot similar to a samovar, used for heating water and brewing tea
9.	Banka	banka - idish; shisha, tunuka, plastmassadan yasalgan, odatda silindrik shaklga ega idish	banka - container; a container made of glass, tin, plastic, usually cylindrical in shape
10.	Belkurak	yerni ag'darish, ochilgan, sochilgan narslarni yig'ish uchu ishlatiladigan uzun dastali temit sopli ish qurol	a long-handled, steel-handled tool used for turning over the ground, picking up loose or scattered objects
11.	Bedon	moy va boshqa suyuqliklarni saqlashda ishlatiladigan idish	a container used to store oil and other liquids

12.	Bodiya	katta mis kosa; tagi baland, qirg'og'i tik, katta idish (lagan)	a large copper bowl; dish looks like a large plate with a high base and steep edges
13.	Bokal	suyuq ichimliklar ichishga mo'ljallangan cho'zinchoq shisha yoki billur idish, qadah	a long glass or crystal vessel for drinking liquid beverages, a goblet
14.	Billur	yuqori navli tiniq oq shisha va undan yasalgan qimmatbaho idish	high-quality clear white glass and an expensive vessel made from it
15.	bolg'acha	kichkina bolg'acha	hammer
16.	Bordon	qobog'ogobog'i olinmagan qamishdan buyraga o'xshatib to'qilgan qalin, dag'al to'shama	"bordon" - a thick, rough mat woven from unbleached reeds in a kidney-shaped pattern.
17.	bo'yra	tozalangan qamish cho'pidan to'qilgan to'shama	a mat woven from cleaned reeds
18.	chakki xalta	qatiq, chakki va sh.k.larni osib qo'yish uchun matodan tayyorlanadigan anjom	"chakki khalta" - cloth -bag is used to hang the sour and chaki (tastes as fermented milk drink/ kefir)
19.	Chambar	meva va boshqa narslarni solib qoyiladigan toldan yasaladigan savat	"chambar" - a wicker basket for holding fruit and other items made of willow wood

Conclusion: This study examined the lexical representativeness and semantic ramification of device-related meronyms in Uzbek and English. By analyzing how device parts are named and categorized in both languages, we identified significant linguistic and cultural patterns. First, the study shows that English exhibits a higher degree of lexical specialization in the names of household appliance parts, often reflecting a more technical or industrial approach. In contrast, in Uzbek there is a prevailing tendency to use more general or multifunctional terms, sometimes based on cultural context or practical usage rather than technical precision. Second, the semantic branching of meronyms reveals how different languages conceptualize objects in terms of their parts. English often exhibits a deeper hierarchical structure of meronyms, while Uzbek prefers more linear or function-oriented semantic groupings. For example, in English, a washing machine may have clearly labeled components such as an "agitator", "drum", and "lint filter" whereas in Uzbek, broader terms such as "drum" or "filter" may cover multiple functions or parts. These differences highlight the influence of cultural, technological, and linguistic factors on vocabulary formation. In addition, the analysis contributes to a broader understanding of lexical systems in typologically diverse languages and can help in such fields as translation studies, language teaching, and computational linguistics.

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